

Regional Wildlife Management Program
for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean

ACTIVITIES REPORT

1993-1996

PROFESSIONAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE STAFF 1993-1996 with STUDENTS of VII,
VIII AND IX PROMOTIONS

From above row sitting left to right:
(Row 1) C. Mo, G. Méndez, R. Montagné, M. McCoy, A. Chediack, J. Fallas, C. Vaughan; (Row 2) S. Cervantes, H. Casasola, L. Piedra, H. Mandujano, M. Mendoza, F. Osorio; (Row 3) H. Vargas, M. Carranza, L. Maffei, M. T. López, M. Retamosa, A. Rodríguez, L. Araya (BIODOC), I. Jiménez, M. Altrichter, R. Tavares, B. Córdoba, M. Araya; (Row 4) I. Torrealba, E. Tabilo, H. Herrera, L. G. Gómez, A. V. Mata, J. Sáenz (several members of PRMVS are not in picture) (photo Claudette Mo)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

REGIONAL IMPACT

- ✓ PRMVS was awarded the Rainforest Alliance's "Ally" award in 1995 in recognition for the impact on Latin American natural resources' conservation and management by PRMVS graduates;
- ✓ Four PRMVS professors received national and international awards of recognition;
- ✓ Eight international institutions provided Fulbright, Sabbatical or Visiting Professors;
- ✓ Twenty institutions provided funding for PRMVS;
- ✓ Cooperative agreements were signed with seven institutions or organizations;
- ✓ Eight international institutions participated in cooperative training or exchange projects;
- ✓ Ninety-two percent of our graduates are working in strategic positions in Latin American natural resources conservation.

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GRADUATE TRAINING PROGRAM

- ✓ Research and teaching staff consisted of 21 professors from seven countries with Universidad Nacional positions, five at the Ph.D. level and 16 with M.Sc. degrees. PRMVS also received the aid of 12 guest professors and researchers;
- ✓ Students from 3 countries participated as research assistants and special students;
- ✓ Student participation since 1987: 90 professionals from 18 Latin American countries, and 5 students from Germany, Spain, and the United States of America. A total of 46 have already graduated, 17 are in thesis work, 23 are undertaking courses. Three were not accepted to graduate studies and 5 left the program for study or employment elsewhere, or for personal reasons.
- ✓ PRMVS graduates are assuming leadership roles in biodiversity-conservation biology projects throughout Latin America with eight directors or chiefs of governmental conservation agencies, 15 university professors, and a variety of other positions in NGOs and governmental agencies.
- ✓ Seven PRMVS graduates are continuing doctoral studies.

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RESEARCH, MONITORING, MANAGEMENT AND OUTREACH BY STAFF

- ✓ Staff carried out twenty-six research projects. Graduate students often develop their thesis within the framework of one of the staff projects. Many are important model wildlife management-conservation biology projects and all provide needed data about neotropical natural resource management;
- ✓ Sixty-two papers were given at international meetings in 9 countries, while 12 papers were presented at national events. Twelve professors and six students, graduates or assistants participated;
- ✓ Ninety publications were produced by PRMVS staff and students between 1992-1996, including 34 books or chapters in books, 28 journal articles, 18 articles in proceedings of scientific meetings and over 30 technical reports;

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OUTREACH THROUGH INFORMATION AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

- ✓ BIODOC, the Wildlife Documentation Center, has accumulated over 3511 books (1749 of which are included in a computerized database), complete collections of six scientific journals, and a partial collection of 270 other scientific journals, and subscribes to 58 scientific publications; it has 6,900 reprints of wildlife-related articles, as well as Wildlife Review Index 1971-1995 on a database CD-ROM disk. BIODOC also contains a complete copy of Wildlife Review (1935-1995) and Zoological Record (1974-1992) for birds, mammals, reptiles and amphibians. BIODOC has over 1,749 technical and institutional reports and theses on file as gray literature;
- ✓ The Remote Sensing and Geographical Information System Laboratory (TELESIG) offers graduate courses, short-courses, and research possibilities; microcomputer facilities include 5 Pentium microcomputers and 2 laptop portable microcomputers for field work. All staff and students are computer-literate, receiving training and refresher courses;
- ✓ The international journal, Vida Silvestre Neotropical was reestablished in 1993 at PRMVS, and has since published volumes 3, 4; and 5 (6 numbers). Publication includes 30 featured articles, 12 short communications, and 35 book reviews;
- ✓ At least three documentary films based on original research were produced;

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FINANCIAL SUPPORT

- ✓ Donors and the Universidad Nacional contributed a total of US\$ 1,505,200 to PRMVS from 1993-96;
- ✓ Funding included: student scholarships, staff salaries, general services, equipment, BIODOC, a student residency and Universidad Nacional foundation overhead;
- ✓ Major funding agencies included: US Fish and Wildlife Service, German Academic Exchange Service, World Wildlife Fund-US, US National Fish and Wildlife Foundation, the Spanish International Cooperation Agency, Organization of American States, and International Resources Development of England.

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Olive Ridley's turtle at Nancite Beach, Santa Rosa National Park.

S. Clusella

OBJECTIVES

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- a) to train professionals in Neotropical Wildlife Management and Conservation so they can contribute to wildlife conservation within the sustainable development strategies of their countries;
- b) to develop methods and techniques for neotropical wildlife management which will enable humans to use, control and conserve wildlife within the sustainable development strategies of each country.
- c) to orient training towards Neotropical sustainable development.
- d) to develop a scientific and technical basis for planning, monitoring and managing wildlife resources, with special emphasis on improving rural development.
- e) to encourage rural involvement in the conservation, control and utilization of wildlife, through outreach, training and technical programs;
- f) to identify the key problems which confront wildlife resources in the region and provide solutions which promote sustainable development on national and regional levels;
- g) to provide services of a regional wildlife management documentation center (BIODOC);
- h) to edit and publish the international journal *Vida Silvestre Neotropical*;
- i) to disseminate appropriate, modern technology to be used in planning, monitoring and management of biological resources in the region.

Three-toed sloth at Avarios del Caribe, Limón, Costa Rica.

This is a Latin American graduate program given "*in situ*". It has a very competitive selection process with an average of 60 students applying for 10-15 positions for each promotion.

H. López

VIIth Promotion at Corcovado National Park, 1995.

GRADUATE TRAINING PROGRAM

C. Vaughan

IXth Promotion en Palo Verde National Park.

Before being admitted to the graduate program, students must approve four required refresher courses and an English language competency exam.

COURSE OF STUDY

This is comprised of 27 months divided into three blocks: a) 2.5 months of refresher undergraduate courses; b) 12 months of 10 graduate courses, three seminars, and two field courses; and c) 12 months of thesis work. One week separates each quarter of 10-11 weeks. Emphasis is placed on biodiversity-wildlife management techniques, community outreach-environmental education and communication, and working as bio-politicians with local and regional conservation issues. Flexibility is allowed in choosing electives during the third quarter. About 40% of the 27 months is spent in field situations. This curriculum has been adjusted several times, through student and staff feedback, to meet changing needs of conservation-wildlife biologists in Latin America.

ELECTIVE COURSES FOR ADVANCED RESEARCH/OUTREACH TOPICS:

- Wildlife Management II
- Conservation Biology
- Analysis and Control of Vertebrate Pests
- Environmental Education and Communication
- Multivariate Statistics
- Experimental Designs
- Geographical Information Systems
- Pesticides and Wildlife
- Wildlife Diseases
- Topics on Wildlife Management
- Wildlife Ethology
- Population Dynamics
- Radio-telemetry
- Tech. in Sociological Research and Extension
- Ornithology
- Management and Conservation of Protected Areas
- Wetlands

Refresher Undergraduate courses:

- Rural Sociology (3^a)
- Behavioral Ecology (3)
- Basic Statistics (3)
- Animal Populatn Ecology (3)

Quarter 1:

- Wildlife Management (3)
- Biometry (3)
- Habitat Evaluation (3)
- Wildlife. Seminar I (1)

Quarter 2:

- Vertebrate Populatn Ecol. (6)
- Wildl. Mgmt. Techniques (3)

Quarter 3:

- Electives I (3)
- Electives II (3)
- Electives III (3)
- Wildlife Seminar II (1)

Quarter 4:

- Thesis Seminar (3)
- Advanced Thesis Topic I (3)
- Community Outreach (3)
- Environmental Education and Communication (2)

Quarter 5:

- Multi-disciplinary Research/ Outreach Project (6)

Quarter 6:

- Thesis (14)

^a= credit

CreditsTotal=60

Ten-week quarter with four introductory undergraduate courses (theory) to bring students up-to-par with basic skills needed to continue with graduate courses.

Q1: First quarter of graduate courses (11 weeks). Principles and theory of wildlife management, common statistical tests and designs, habitat evaluation with emphasis in GIS computer-aided uses and principles and theory of sustainable development are taught.

Q2: Six-week field course in population ecology given in two sites in Costa Rica. Practice in formulation of hypothesis, collection of field data, statistical analysis of data, and presentation (oral and written) of results is stressed. Main techniques used in wildlife management are covered in second course during three weeks.

Q3: During third quarter, three electives are chosen from a list of offered courses (see side-bar). Independent topics can also be considered. Seminar explores techniques in vertebrate pest analysis and control or other areas of current interest.

Q4: Students write thesis proposals. Seminar teaches proposal writing techniques and students use one elective to actually write their proposal. Environmental Education and Community Outreach courses concentrate on techniques for communicating and working with rural human populations.

Q5: A 10-week field course where students choose a topic (research, outreach, management plan, etc.) and carry it through. Involves sampling biota and work with rural communities in sustainable development themes.

Q6: Based on original field research of a minimum of 8 months with 4 months analysis and preparation for defense.

STUDENT INFORMATION

From 1987 to 1996, 95 students were admitted to the "Refresher" term, and upon completion 87 were accepted into our graduate school. Currently, 46 of our students have graduated. Their country of origin is varied, with the majority from Central and South America (90). Five students were admitted from North America and Europe.

The following tables give details on student selection and graduation rates.

Number of Students Admitted to the Program and to Graduate Studies.

Promotion	Year	Refresher Courses	Graduate Studies
I	1987	11	11
II	1988	13	12
III	1989	10	10
IV	1991	9	8
V	1992	13	10
VI	1993	15	13
VII	1995	14	14
VIII	1996	10	9
TOTAL		95	87

Number of Admitted Students by Country of Origin (1987-96).

Country	Refresher courses		Graduate school			
	Admitted	Accepted	Graduated	Left	Class work	Thesis work
Argentina	7	7	5		2	
Brazil	2	1			1	
Bolivia	3	3	1		2	
Chile	1	1			1	
Colombia	8	8	4		4	
Costa Rica	18	17	8	1	3	5
Dominican Rep.	1					
Ecuador	2	2	2			
Spain	2	2			2	
El Salvador	3	3	1			2
Germany	1	1			1	
Guatemala	5	5	3		1	1
Honduras	4	3	2			1
Mexico	10	9	7			2
Nicaragua	8	6	2		3	1
Panama	5	5	3		1	1
Paraguay	2	2	1			1
Peru	4	4	3		1	
Uruguay	2	2	2			
USA	2	1				1
Venezuela	5	5	2		1	2
Total	95	87	46	1	23	17

Bird watching during an ornithology field trip, VII Promotion

L. Gómez

WHAT SOME OF OUR GRADUATES ARE CURRENTLY DOING

Name	Country	Current Work
Juan Diego Alfaro	Costa Rica	Chief of research of La Amistad Biosphere Reserve in Costa Rica.
José Luis Altuve	Venezuela	Professor in the Graduate Program in Renewable Natural Resources in Aquatic and Wildlife Management, at the Experimental National University of the Western Plains, Guanare, Portuguesa, Venezuela.
Marcelo Aranda	Mexico	Associate researcher at the Institute of Ecology in Veracruz, Mexico. Ph.D. candidate at UNAM in Mexico. Teaches in new M.Sc. wildlife program at Institute of Ecology.
Jacobo Araúz	Panama	Professor at the National University of Panama. Works on projects that ANCON develops on conservation of the Panama Canal watershed.
Marta Araújo	Panama	Consultant to the Natural Resource Department of Panama (INRENARE).
Javier Beltrán	Argentina	Employee of the World Conservation Monitoring Center, England.
Never Bonino	Argentina	Chief of the Ecology and Wildlife Management Group of Bariloche Experimental Station of the National Institute of Agrarian Technology (INTA), Argentina.
José Calvopiña	Ecuador	Former director of Charles Darwin Station, Galapagos. Currently employee of Antisana Foundation doing management plans in Ecuador and Peru.
Eduardo Carrillo	Costa Rica	Ph.D. candidate at University of Massachusetts, USA. Staff professor and researcher at the PRMVS, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica.
Carlos Cerrato	Honduras	Professor in the Biology Department of the Autonomous University of Honduras.
Silvia Chalukian	Argentina	Professor in the Natural Resources Division at El Zamorano, Pan-American Agricultural School, Honduras.
Federico Chinchilla	Costa Rica	Curator at Simón Bolívar National Zoo; coordinator for Spanish OTS (Organization of Tropical Studies) courses on Tropical Ecology, Costa Rica. Field courses instructor, Monteverde Institute, Costa Rica. Professor of biology in Universidad de Costa Rica at Guanacaste Regional Center, Liberia.
Alfredo Cuarón	Mexico	Ph.D. candidate at Cambridge University, England. Researcher at Institute of Ecology, UNAM, Mexico.
Nélida Edith García	Argentina	Biologist at the Wildlife Sub-Directorate of the Economy Ministry, Viedma, Rio Negro, Argentina.
María José González	Guatemala	Executive Director of the Interamerican Foundation for Tropical Research (FIIT), a Guatemalan non-profit organization dedicated to wildlife and wildlands research and management.
Maritza Guido	El Salvador	Advisor to the National Center of Agricultural Technology, El Salvador.
Iliá Hartasánchez	Mexico	Ph.D. student at Michigan State University, USA.
Daniel Hernández (†)	Costa Rica	Deceased in 1996. Was Associate Professor at the Regional Wildlife Management Program, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Specialty was migratory terrestrial bird ecology.
Oscar Lara	Guatemala	Director and professor of the Biology Department at San Carlos University, Guatemala City, Guatemala.
Martín Lezama	Nicaragua	Professor at Ecology Dept. of Central American University, Managua, Nicaragua.
Lorena López de Buen	Mexico	Ph.D. student in Mexico.
Nancy López	Paraguay	Former Chief of the Fauna Division of the National Parks and Wildlife Service and of the Biological Inventories Department of the National Museum of Paraguay.
Leda Malavassi	Costa Rica	Director of a private school in Costa Rica.
Ignacio March	Mexico	Researcher and professor of the Center of Ecological Research of the Southeast (CIES), a Mexican NGO working on environmental problems in southern Mexico. Ph. D. Candidate.

Continued

Name	Country	Current Work
César Márquez	Colombia	Consultant for GEF biodiversity project at the Choco region, for Ecofondo and NGO's in raptor rehabilitation; environmental education volunteer. Currently studying swallow-tailed kite migration between North and South America.
Leonel Marineros	Honduras	Professor in the Biology Department of the Autonomous University of Honduras; also, working with UNEP on a natural resources project.
Javier Monge	Costa Rica	Works in the CIPET of the Ministry of Education of Costa Rica. Occasional professor of the University of Costa Rica.
Rodrigo Morera	Costa Rica	Consulate for Costa Rica in David, Panama.
Martha Motte	Paraguay	Taking post-graduate courses in Sweden. Works at the Natural History Museum of Paraguay.
Eduardo Naranjo	Mexico	Researcher and professor at the Center of Ecological Research of the Southeast (CIES), a Mexican NGO working on environmental problems in southern Mexico. Ph. D. student at the University of Florida, Gainesville, Florida.
Sonia Navarro	Mexico	Professor at Guadalajara University, Mexico.
Cecilia Pacheco	Ecuador	Works at a local NGO in Ecuador.
Enrique Páez	Uruguay	Research biologist at the Division of Marine Mammals of the National Institute of Fisheries (INAPE). Taught a population dynamics course at the PRMVS, National University, Costa Rica.
Arnoldo Paniagua	Nicaragua	Employee of Ministry of Agriculture, Managua, Nicaragua. Currently organizing the reduction of financial debt of cattle ranchers who reforest pastures in Nicaragua, at request of Minister. Plan has been approved by World Bank.
María del Pilar Rivas	Colombia	Works at a local NGO in Colombia.
Joel Sáenz	Peru	Associate professor and researcher at the PRMVS, National University, Costa Rica.
Carlos Salcedo	Peru	Ph.D. student in Canada.
Ronald Sánchez	Costa Rica	Professor of zoology and coordinator of the biology career at the Regional Center of the University of Costa Rica, San Ramón, Costa Rica.
Pedro Sánchez	Colombia	Professor at the National University, Bogota, Colombia. Private consultant.
Wilfredo Segura	Costa Rica	Associate professor at the PRMVS and researcher at GIS Telesig Laboratory at UNA Costa Rica. Currently employed as GIS specialist in screw-worm eradication program of USAID in Costa Rica.
Romeo Spinola	Uruguay	Consultant for the United Nations sponsored wetland project in Uruguay. Director of Durazno Zoo, Uruguay. Ph.D. student at Pennsylvania State University, USA.
Isa Torrealba	Venezuela	Associate professor and researcher at the PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica.
Eduardo Velazco	Colombia	Subdirector of the Environmental Heritage Department of the Corporation of Cali Valley (CVC), Colombia.
Jorge Ventocilla	Panama	Coordinator of the Environmental Education Program at the Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, Panama.
Roberto Vides	Argentina	Director of the Graduate Program in Wildlands Management at the University of Tucuman; guest professor at CATIE; consultant at the Green Iguana Foundation in Costa Rica.
Lillíán Villalba	Bolivia	Director of the Natural History Museum of Bolivia, La Paz, Bolivia.
Grace Wong	Costa Rica	Ph.D. student at University of Massachusetts. Staff professor and researcher at the PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica.
Teresa Zúñiga	Nicaragua	Head of a local NGO and IUCN consultant for Nicaragua and Honduras.

THESIS WORK 1993-1996 (chronologically)**1993**

Salcedo Cardeña, Carlos. 1993. Hormonal evaluation of the reproductive cycle of birds of the genus *Ara* in captivity (Peru-IV Promotion).

Marineros Sánchez, Leonel. 1993. Scarlet macaw *Ara macao* (Psittaciformes: Psittacidae): Ecology, tourism and guidelines for its management in the Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica (Honduras-IV Promotion).

Araúz González, Jacobo. 1993. Conservation status of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii citrinellus*) in its original distributional range (Panama-IV Promotion).

Cabrera Belloso, Milton. 1993. The ecosystem Cerro Cahí: An ecological island in Petén, Guatemala (Chapter 1). Influence of vegetation structure on abundance of some vertebrates in Petén Guatemala (Chapter II) (Guatemala-I Promotion - submission pending).

Torrealba Suárez, Isa. 1993. Ecology of peccary groups (*Tayassu tajacu*) and the damage they inflict on plantations around La Selva Biological Station, Costa Rica (Venezuela-IV Promotion).

Capture of a collared peccary at La Selva, Sarapiquí.

Araúz Almengor, Martha. 1993. Hatching rate in marked nests of the ridley turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) in Playa Ostional Wildlife Refuge, Ostional, Guanacaste, Costa Rica (Panama-IV Promotion).

1994

Motte Paredes, Martha. 1994. Abundance, distribution and impact of predation by crocodiles (*Crocodylus acutus* Cuvier 1807) on cattle in ranches around the Río Grande de Tárcoles (Paraguay-IV Promotion).

Beltrán Sola, Javier. 1994. Feeding habits and diet of *Procnias tricarunculata*: A mixed approach to evaluate parameters which influence its role as a seed disperser (Argentina-V Promotion).

Naranjo Peñera, Eduardo. 1994. Abundance, habitat use and diet of Baird's tapir (*Tapirus bairdii*) in Corcovado National Park, Costa Rica (Mexico-V Promotion).

Rivas Pava, Pilar. 1994. Comparison of the structure of the community of small mammals in a tropical rainforest with different levels of alteration, La Selva, Costa Rica (Colombia-V Promotion).

Zúñiga, Teresa. 1994. The agouti, *Agouti paca*, in Barro del Colorado Wildlife Refuge: Contributions to its management (Nicaragua-V Promotion).

Spínola Parallada, Romeo. 1994. Habitat, spatial use and ecology of the otter (*Lutra longicaudis*) in La Selva Biological Reserve (Uruguay-V Promotion).

Pacheco Sempertegui, Cecilia. 1994. Feeding habits and seasonal habitat use of the crested guan (*Penelope purpurascens*) in the tropical dry forest, Santa Rosa National Park, Costa Rica (Ecuador-V Promotion).

Sánchez Palomino, Pedro. 1994. Density, habitat use and food availability of the guatusa (*Dasyprocta punctata*) in the tropical dry forest of Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica (Colombia-V Promotion).

Chinchilla Romero, Federico. 1994. Jaguar (*Panthera onca*), puma (*Felis concolor*), and ocelot (*Felis pardalis*) diets: Two methods to evaluate their relative abundances in Corcovado National Park, Costa Rica (Costa Rica-V Promotion).

Sáenz Méndez, Joel. 1994. Ecology of the coatimundi (*Nasua narica*) and its role as seed disperser in the tropical dry forest (Peru-V Promotion).

1995

Segura, Wilfredo. 1995. Use of remote sensors and GIS in the evaluation of potential habitat for white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*), Bagacés, Guanacaste, Costa Rica (Costa Rica-V Promotion).

Páez Olarte, Enrique. 1995. Population dynamics of the South American fur seal (*Arctocephalus australis*) in Uruguay (Uruguay-VI Promotion).

Ruíz Pérez, Gustavo. 1995. Nesting ecology of the turtle *Trachemys scripta* (Testudines, Emydidae) in San Sebastian Lake, Caño Negro, Costa Rica (Nicaragua-III Promotion).

López de Buen, Lorena. 1995. Domestic feral cats (*Felis catus*) in an urban area of Costa Rica: Sterilization, activity, home ranges and feeding habits (Mexico-VI Promotion).

Enríquez Rocha, Paula. 1995. Relative abundance, habitat use and popular knowledge about strigiforms (owls) in a tropical rainforest, Costa Rica (Mexico-VI Promotion submission pending).

Rangel Salazar, José Luis. 1995. Bird diversity in the understory of banana plantations in Costa Rica (Mexico-VI Promotion - submission pending).

1996

- López, Jorge Erwin.** 1996. Food habitats of frugivorous bats and their role in seed dispersal in secondary forests (Guatemala-VI Promotion).
- Canales, Angel.** 1996. Abundance and differential distribution of kingfishers (Alcedinidae) in the canals of Tortuguero National Park (Peru-VI Promotion).
- García Precioso, Nélide Edith.** 1996. Ecology of the Central American cacomistle (*Bassariscus sumichrasti*) in a Costa Rican cloud forest (Argentina-VI Promotion).
- Lezama, Martín.** 1996. Rodents in irrigated rice paddies: Abundance, microhabitats, inter-patch movements, and use of artificial perches by raptors as a method of biological control (Nicaragua-VI Promotion- submission pending).
- Vargas, Mario Chacón.** 1996. Captive management and an economic evaluation of tepezcuintle breeding (*Agouti paca*) in the Atlantic region of Costa Rica (Costa Rica-VI Promotion)
- Moreira Avila, Rodrigo.** 1996. Habitat use and important plant species in the diet of howler monkeys (*Alouatta palliata*) and white-faced capuchins (*Cebus capucinus*) in dry tropical forest (Costa Rica, IV Promotion)

tion of the manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus* L.) in Tortuguero Conservation Area (C. Vaughan, major advisor).

- López, Hugo** (Colombia). Use of forest fragments by resident and migratory passerine birds (J. Fallas, major advisor).
- Millán, José** (Venezuela). Application of an environmental education method with emphasis on the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) in Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica (C. Charpentier, major advisor).
- Mora, Geisel** (Costa Rica). Migration patterns of terrestrial migratory birds on the Atlantic coast of Costa Rica (M. McCoy, major advisor).
- Paniagua, Arnoldo** (Nicaragua). Effects of cattle grazing on wetlands in Palo Verde National Park (M. McCoy, major advisor).
- Sierra, Claudine** (Argentina). Evaluation of eradication methods for feral swine (*Sus scrofa*) on Cocos Island, Costa Rica (M. McCoy, major advisor).
- Tabilo, Elier** (Chile). Importance of wetlands for migratory birds in Costa Rica (M. McCoy, major advisor).

THESIS TOPICS in 1996 (VII promotion):

Students that initiated field work in May 1996:

- Altrichter, Mariana** (Argentina). Feeding strategies and social structure of the white-lipped peccary (*Tayassu pecari*) in Corcovado National Park (C. Drews, major advisor).
- Fernández, María Teresa** (Spain). Resource use and area of influence of a pollinating bat colony in a tropical dry forest (C. Drews, major advisor).
- Gómez, Luis Germán** (Colombia). Habitat use and population density trends of white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) in La Emilia Farm, Guanacaste, Costa Rica (J. Sáenz, major advisor).
- González, Jorge** (Costa Rica). Migratory and resident bird diversity in coffee plantations with and without shade trees in the Central Valley of Costa Rica (J. Sáenz, major advisor).
- Hernández, César** (Nicaragua). Evaluation of pesticide impact on macroinvertebrates in two streams in San José de la Montaña, Barva, Heredia (L. Castillo, major advisor).
- Herrera, Heidi** (Nicaragua). Behavior of the Pipridae family and conservation of its habitat in Tortuguero Conservation Area (M. I. Di Mare, major advisor).
- Jiménez, Belkys** (Panamá). Avifauna habitat use of area under differing degrees of perturbation in Caño Negro National Wildlife Refuge (C. Hidalgo, major advisor).
- Jiménez, Ignacio** (Spain). Evaluation of the potential recupera-

STUDENTS ACCEPTED in 1996:

VIIIth Promotion students that began graduate classwork on April 29, 1996.

- | | |
|--------------------|------------|
| Oliver Bach | Germany |
| Jaime Cabrera | Colombia |
| Henry Campero | Bolivia |
| Fabricio Carbonell | Peru |
| Vicente Meza | Costa Rica |
| Francisco Osorio | Bolivia |
| Rocio Polanco | Colombia |
| Roberto Ruz | Guatemala |
| Roberval Tavares | Brazil |

Penned white-tailed deer at Cañas, Guanacaste, Costa Rica.

L. G. Gómez

WHO ARE WE

TEACHING AND RESEARCH STAFF FROM UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL that participated at PRMVS

Name	Degree	Emphasis, Institution. <i>Type of involvement at PRMVS (courses taught, graduate committee, etc.).</i> Country of origin.
Gerardo Barrantes	M.Sc.	Economical Ecology, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Ecological Economics.</i> Costa Rica.
Jorge Camacho	Ph.D.	Animal genetics improvement, Polytechnical University of Valencia, Spain. <i>Biometry.</i> Costa Rica.
Montserrat Carbonell	Ph.D.	Biological Sciences, Cardiff College, University of Wales, United Kingdom. <i>Thesis Seminar.</i> Spain.
Eduardo Carrillo	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Introduction to Microcomputers - Vertebrate Population Ecology (field course).</i> Costa Rica.
Victor Cartín	Ph.D.	Agroecology, University of Wisconsin, USA. <i>Wildlife Seminar (Vertebrate Pest Control).</i> Costa Rica.
Luisa Castillo	M.Sc.	Ecotoxicology, University of Metz, France. <i>Thesis Advisor.</i> Costa Rica.
María Isabel Di Mare	Ph.D.	Wildlife and Fisheries Sciences, Texas A&M University, USA. <i>Conservation Biology - Wildlife Management - Thesis Seminar.</i> Costa Rica.
Carlos Drews	Ph.D.	Wildlife Ethology. Cambridge University, United Kingdom. <i>Behavioral Ecology - Wildlife Ethology.</i> Colombia.
Jorge Fallas	M.Sc.	Natural Resources, Univ. of Michigan, USA. <i>Habitat Evaluation, Remote Sensing and Geographical Information Systems.</i> Costa Rica
Luis Gámez	M.Sc.	Ecological Economics, Anthropology. University of Berkeley, California, USA. <i>Ecological Economics.</i> Costa Rica
Daniel Hernández (†)	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Ornithology, Wildlife Management Techniques.</i> Costa Rica.
Carmen Hidalgo	M.Sc.	Biology, University of Costa Rica. <i>Ornithology and thesis advisor.</i> Costa Rica.
Gerardo Jiménez	M.Sc.	Ecological Economics, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Ecological Economics.</i> Costa Rica.
Michael McCoy	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, Computer Sciences, Humboldt State University, USA. <i>Basic Statistics - Biometry - Advanced Statistics.</i> Co-Editor of Vida Silvestre Neotropical. USA.
Claudette Mo	D.M.V.	University of Sao Paulo, Brazil & M.S.: Veterinary Science/Wildlife Ecology, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA. <i>Wildlife Diseases.</i> Brazil.
Isabel Román	M.Sc.	Rural Sociology, University of Costa Rica. <i>Rural Sociology, Community Outreach, Techniques in Sociological Research and Extension.</i> Costa Rica
Joel Sáenz	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Integrated Project - Vertebrate Population Ecology (field course).</i> Wildlife Management. Peru.
Isa Torrealba	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Radio-telemetry Seminar - Environmental Education and Communication.</i> Venezuela.
Emilio Vargas	M.Sc.	Rural Sociology, University of Costa Rica. <i>Rural Sociology, Community Outreach, Techniques in Sociological Research and Extension - Integrated Project.</i> Costa Rica
Christopher Vaughan	M.Sc.	Wildlands Management, University of Costa Rica-CATIE, Costa Rica. <i>Ecology of Terrestrial Vertebrates - Thesis Seminar - Conservation Biology - Wildlife Management - Seminar (Sustainable Development) - Seminar (Radio-Telemetry).</i> Co-Editor of Vida Silvestre Neotropical. USA.
Grace Wong	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Environmental Education and Communication - Wildlife Management (Seminar).</i> Costa Rica.

GUEST PROFESSORS AND RESEARCHERS

Name	Degree	Emphasis, Institution. <i>Type of involvement at PRMVS (courses taught, graduate committee, etc.).</i> Country of origin.
Richard Alldredge	Ph.D.	Statistics, Texas A&M Univ., USA. On sabbatical leave from the University of Washington. <i>Assisted PRMVS staff and students on research designs. Assisted in Basic Statistics and Biometry courses.</i> USA.
Marcelo Aranda	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Assisted in Vertebrate Population Ecology field course: short course on animal track identification.</i> Mexico.
Lise Caron	Ph.D.	Biology, University of Sherbrooke. Canada. On sabbatical leave from the University of Moncton, New Brunswick, Canada. <i>Assisted in the project on "Management and restoration of wildlife in rural areas of Costa Rica". Developed an inter-institutional agreement between the University of Moncton and the PRMVS for future collaboration.</i> Canada.
Balduino De Roover	Ing.	University of Gent, Belgium. GIS and Remote Sensing specialist. <i>Collaboration with TELESIG.</i> Belgium.
Rebecca Field	Sc.D.	The Johns Hopkins University, USA. <i>Assisted in the Vertebrate Population Ecology field course.</i> USA..
Donald Forrester	Ph.D.	Zoology, Univ. of California, Davis, USA. <i>Guest lecturer in the Wildlife Diseases course.</i> USA.
Todd Fuller	Ph.D.	Wildlife Ecology, Univ. Wisconsin-Madison, USA. <i>Assisted in the Vertebrate Population Ecology field course.</i> USA.
Randall García	M.Sc.	Tourism, Ecology. ULACIT, Costa Rica. <i>Professor of the Wildland Administration course.</i> Costa Rica.
Beth Middleton	Ph.D.	Botany. Iowa State University, Ames. <i>Gave training session on microhistological techniques in vegetative identification of wildlife scats.</i> USA..
José Manuel Mora	Ph.D.	Wildlife and Fisheries Sciences, Texas A&M Univ., USA. <i>Professor of the Integrated Project course.</i> Costa Rica.
Enrique Páez	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS, UNA, Costa Rica. <i>Professor of the Population Dynamics course.</i> Uruguay.
Jaime Rau	Ph.D.	Biological Sciences, University of Sevilla, Spain. <i>Professor of the courses Vertebrate Population Ecology, Integrated Project, Management and Conservation of Protected Areas.</i> Chile.
Stan Tomkiewicz, Jr.	Ph.D.	Director, environmental programs, TELONICS. <i>Organized and presented a regional radio-telemetry workshop at PRMVS.</i> USA.
Tom Yuill	Ph.D.	Wildlife Management, University of Wisconsin-Madison. Director of the Institute for Environmental Studies. <i>Guest lecturer in the Wildlife Diseases course.</i> USA.

E. Carrillo

Capture of a jaguar at Corcovado National Park

RESEARCH ASSISTANTS AND SPECIAL STUDENTS

Name	Degree	Emphasis, Institution. Type of involvement at PRMVS. Country of origin.
Claudia Ceballos	D.V.M.	University of Valle, Colombia. Assisted in olive ridley sea turtle project.
Kristen Conway	B.Sc.	Environmental Studies, Allegheny College, USA. Assisted in scarlet macaw project. 1993-1994.
Henry Chaves		Forestry. Assistant in TELESIG.
José Díaz		Assistant in the project, Interspecific relationships between jaguars and white-lipped peccaries.
Lorna Flormoe	B.S.	University of Oregon. Assisted in Scarlet Macaw Project.
Carlos Madriz	B.S.	Forestry. Worked on applications of GIS and Remote Sensing to second growth forest management.
Jill Meyer	B.S.	Assisted in two research projects: 1) the olive ridley sea turtle and 2) the "Interspecific relationships between jaguars and white-lipped peccaries".
Jorge Montero	B.S.	Biology at UNA, Costa Rica. Assisted in the ecology of pollinating bat project.
Mark Myers	B.S.	Kenyon College, USA. Assisted in scarlet macaw and tapir projects. USA.
Nicole Nemeth	B.S.	Biology, Grinnell College, USA. Assisted in the scarlet macaw project.
Birgit Priem	B.S.	University of Hannover, Germany. Assisted in the ecology of pollinating bat project.
Jorge Quesada		Marine Biology at UNA, Costa Rica. Assisted in sea turtle project.
Deborah Rodríguez	B.S.	CATIE, Costa Rica. Assisted in the peccary project at La Selva.
Wilfredo Segura	M.Sc.	Wildlife Management, PRMVS. Assisted in the project on Management and restoration of wildlife in rural areas of Costa Rica.
Andrés Vaughan		Biology at Universidad de Costa Rica, Costa Rica. Assisted in waterhole studies.
James Zook	B.S.	Biology. Assisted in migratory bird project at Tortuguero and in training courses.

STAFF PROJECTS

Research, monitoring, management, and outreach projects aimed at providing alternative natural resource uses necessary to achieve "sustainable development".

Birds

- Reproduction of the boat-billed heron (*Cochlearius cochlearius*) in the Tempisque river. M. Carbonell.
- Monitoring of migratory and resident birds in Costa Rica. D. Hernández.
- Ecology and management of the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) in the Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica. C. Vaughan.

Mammals

- Interspecific relationships between jaguars and white-lipped peccaries. E. Carrillo and J. Sáenz.
- Applied ecology of pollinating bats. C. Drews,
- Home range and feeding habits of peccaries (*Tayassu tajacu*) in a tropical rainforest. I. Torrealba, J. Rau and E. Carrillo.
- Analysis of the predator-prey interaction between peccaries and felids by means of radiotelemetry and GIS in La Selva, Costa Rica. I. Torrealba.
- Reforestation of the tropical dry forest by seed dispersing mammals. C. Vaughan.
- Ecology of the cacomistle (*Bassariscus sumichrasti*) in Braulio Carrillo National Park. C. Vaughan.
- Conservation of the squirrel monkey in Manuel Antonio National Park, Quepos. G. Wong and E. Carrillo.

Reptiles

- Monitoring of olive ridley turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) populations in Playa Nancite, Costa Rica. C. Mo.

Management

- Management and restoration of wildlife in rural areas of Costa Rica. M. I. Di Mare.

- Rehabilitation and release of wildlife: criteria and feasibility. C. Drews.
- Efficiency of a mechanical, explosive alarm system to control damage caused by black-bellied whistling-ducks (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) in rice fields, Guanacaste, Costa Rica. M. McCoy.
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- Restoration of a freshwater marsh in Palo Verde National Park. M. McCoy.
- Diagnosis of water resources in San José de la Montaña. C. Mo.

GIS

- Evaluation and conservation of soils in Costa Rica: Evaluation, adaptation and application of the most commonly used models. J. Fallas.
- Evaluation of radar data of C-band with polarization HH and VV for forestry applications in Costa Rica. J. Fallas.
- Forestry monitoring using remote sensing and integrated management of watersheds in Costa Rica. J. Fallas.
- Mapping of the biodiversity of biological resources in Costa Rica by means of remote sensing and GIS. J. Fallas.
- Secondary forests in the Central Pacific Region of Costa Rica. J. Fallas.
- Modeling the alternatives in wildlife management with GIS in the Central Pacific Region of Costa Rica. J. Fallas.
- Digital data base for Iguana Reserve, Costa Rica. J. Fallas.

Human Dimensions

- Community involvement in sustainable management of wildlife in Costa Rica. G. Wong, E. Carrillo and I. Torrealba,
- Ecosystem exploitation and the environmental issue in Costa Rica. E. Vargas.
- Production of a series of short television programs entitled "So you don't forget me...". G. Wong and E. Carrillo.

The "Golden Frog" Rain Forest Alliance "Ally" award.

C. Drews

AWARDS AND DISTINCTIONS

- **The Rain Forest Alliance "Ally" Award for Pioneering Neotropical Graduate Conservation Education**

Because of the distinguished role our graduates have played in natural resource conservation in Latin America, The **Rainforest Alliance** bestowed upon the Regional Wildlife Management Program the award "**Rain Forest Alliance Ally**". **Claudette Mo**, then director of PRMVS, attended the gala awards ceremony April 5, 1995 at Plaza Hotel, New York City in the company of various celebrities. **Ted Turner**, of Turner Broadcast, Inc., was awarded the "Rain Forest Alliance Champion Award" for his outstanding work in conservation. The award is given each year to a conservation organization and to an individual who have shown outstanding dedication and success in conservation work. Both Dr. Mo and Mr. Turner received a golden frog trophy in the awards ceremony.

- **Roberto Brenes Mesen Award For Conservation Work In Costa Rica and The Neotropics**

Since 1991, the Universidad Nacional has awarded biannually the Roberto Brenes Mesen Award to an academican who demonstrates the highest academic qualities of the institution. On March 28, 1995, in a official ceremony presided by President Rose Marie Ruiz and attended by over 50 distinguished university officials and academicians,

the award was bestowed on **C. Vaughan**. The rationale motivating the Academic Commission to years of dedication towards Neotropical wildlife and wildland conservation. This included co-founding the PRMVS, pioneer ecological work with over 20 graduate students on many Neotropical mammal species, his publications (8 books and over 150 scientific and technical papers) and more than 50 talks on neotropical conservation throughout the world.

- **Member Of The Scientific Committee For Global Change Institute**

Since 1994 **J. Fallas** has served as member of the Scientific Advisory Committee of Inter-American Institute for Global Change Research (IAI) located in San Jose dos Campos, Brazil.

- **John Napier Medal In Primatology for Distinguished Doctorate Work**

C. Drews, visiting professor at PRMVS since 1995, was awarded the **John Napier Medal 1995** by The British Primatological Society, during their yearly meeting in London, England. This award is given every two years in recognition of the best Ph.D. dissertation in the field of primatology carried out in a British university.

- **Outstanding Scholar Award by The Land and Seas Sciences Faculty**

On March 30, 1995, at a ceremony presided by UNA President Lic. Rose Marie Ruiz and distinguished university officials, Prof. **C. Vaughan** was declared the 1995 outstanding academican of the Land and Sea Sciences Faculty. After the awards ceremony, Prof. Vaughan opened the 1995 school year for the Faculty with the keynote address entitled "Conservation of a Neotropical psittacid".

- **Academic Distinction**

In 1994, the Gran Mariscal de Ayacucho Foundation (Venezuela) distinguished **I. Torrealba** with a \$10,000 award for having the best academic grade average of the IV Promotion of PRMVS.

INTELLECTUAL PRODUCTION, OUTREACH AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

PRESENTATIONS AT PROFESSIONAL MEETINGS

1993

- Carbonell, M.** Reproductive success of the boat-billed heron (*Cochlearius cochlearius*) on the Tempisque river, Costa Rica. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. Poster. May.
- Damon, C. and C. Vaughan.** Ecotourism and wildlife conservation in Costa Rica: Potential for a sustainable partnership. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Drews, C.** Road kills of animals by public traffic in Nikumi National Park, Tanzania. Poster. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San Jose, Costa Rica. September.
- Fallas, J.** The use of Band C radar in classification of land use in Guanacaste, Costa Rica. VI Latin-American Congress of Remote Perception. Cartagena, Colombia. October.
- Fallas, J.** TELESIG: Spatial technology available for sustainable development. International Radar Conference. San José, Costa Rica.
- Fallas, J.** Use of C band radar in the characterization of vegetative cover in the tropical dry forest. International Radar Conference. San José, Costa Rica. November.
- Hartasánchez, I.** Aerial surveys: A feasible technique for management and conservation of aquatic birds and their habitats, or a double-edged sword? First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Hernández, D., L. F. Corrales and R. Soto.** Birds of the Tivives Mangrove Reserve, Costa Rica. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Hernández, D.** Habitat use of ducks (Anatidae) in a seasonal marsh in Costa Rica. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Hernández, D.** Monitoring stations for avifauna of Tortuguero; 1st year results. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Hernández, D.** Mist netting for monitoring birds in neotropical forest communities in Costa Rica. Workshop on mist net use to monitor bird populations. Point Reyes Bird Observatory, California. October.
- McCoy, M. and J. M. Rodríguez.** Monthly numbers of wild ducks in the lower watershed of the Tempisque River, Guanacaste, during the dry seasons between 1986-1990. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- McCoy, M., E. Aragón, G. Herra-Avella and L. E. Rodríguez.** Irrigated rice cultivation and waterfowl: Methods to reduce the conflict. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Mo, C. L., T. C. Moermond, E. Santana and J. J. Huff.** Evaluation of predator risks to wild ducks (*Anas platyrhynchos*). I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Mo, C.** Ostional: A case of symbiosis man-sea-turtle. Latin-American Herpetology Congress. Campiñas, Brazil. 12-19 December.
- Morera, R. A.** Preliminary observations of the food habits, reproduction, use of territory and preferred habitats of the great currawong (*Crax rubra*) in a dry forest of Costa Rica. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Naranjo, E., T. Zúñiga and J. R. Rau.** The relation between species richness and size of protected areas in Costa Rica. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Rau, J. R, D. R. Martínez and A. Muñoz-Pederos.** Trophic ecology of pumas in southern South America. Poster. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Rau, J.** Puma (*Felis concolor*) predation on the Pudu (*Pudu pudu*) and European hare (*Lepus capensis*) in temperate rainforests in southern South America. Poster. XXI International Union of Game Biologists Congress. Halifax, Canada. August.
- Rau, J.** The role of the Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean in the formation of graduates in Latin America. III International Congress on Natural Resource Management: Integrated Approach for Development. Pucon, Temuco, Chile. November.
- Sánchez, J. and D. Hernández.** Abundance, population structure, and diet of *Acanhidops bairdii* and *Haplospiza rustica* in Talamanca. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Sánchez, J. and D. Hernández.** An introduction to bird monitoring activities in Costa Rica and Central America. Poster. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Smith, A. and D. Hernández.** First Costa Rican register of the lark sparrow (*Chondestes grammacus*). I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.
- Savitsky, B. and J. Fallas.** Gap analysis in Costa Rica: Overview of an ongoing project. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Schutt, A. and C. Vaughan.** Incorporating wildlife into development: The case of Curú Wildlife Refuge and farm. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Torrealba, I. and J. Rau.** Home range and population estimation of collared peccaries in a Costa Rican tropical humid forest. Poster. XXI International Union of Game Biologists Congress. Halifax, Canada. August.
- Torrealba, I. and J. R. Rau.** Damage to croplands by collared peccaries in a isolated neotropical forest. Poster. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.
- Vaughan, C.** Ecology and management perspectives of the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) in Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica. I National Ornithological Congress. Heredia, Costa Rica. May.

Claudette Mo at the International Environmental Economics Congress, San José, Costa Rica.

Vaughan, C. Regional wildlife management program in Mesoamerica and the Caribbean: A case study of training, research and outreach in situ (1987-1992). VII Annual Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology. Tempe, Arizona. June.

Vaughan, C. The scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) triad in Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica: Tourists, local residents, and the bird. VII Annual Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology. Tempe, Arizona. June.

Vaughan, C. Integrating resource uses in neotropical forest ecosystems: The Costa Rican example. XXI International Union of Game Biologists Congress. Halifax, Canada. August.

Vaughan, C. The state of biodiversity in Costa Rica. IX National Agronomy and Natural Resources Congress. San Jose, Costa Rica. August.

Vaughan, C. and M. McCoy. Latin American Wildlife Management graduate programs: A case study of training, research and outreach in situ. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.

Vaughan, C. Food habits of the brown caiman (*Caiman crocodrilus*) in Caño Negro Biological Reserve. Poster. XII Latin-American Herpetology Congress. Campinas, Brazil. 12-19 December.

Witmer, G., M. Rodríguez y C. Vaughan. Aspects of felid predator control and conservation in Costa Rica. First International Wildlife Management Congress. San José, Costa Rica. September.

1994

Aráuz, M. and C. Mo. Hatching rates for *Lepidochelys olivacea* in Playa Ostional, Guanacaste, Costa Rica. Poster. XIV Annual Symposium on Sea Turtle Biology and Conservation. Hilton Head Island, South Carolina, USA. March.

Aráuz, M. and R. A. Morera. Status of marine turtles (*Dermochelys coriacea*, *Chelonia agassizi* and *Lepidochelys olivacea*) at Playa Naranjo, Parque Nacional Santa Rosa, Costa Rica. 14th Annual Symposium on Sea Turtle Biology and Conservation. Hilton Head Island, South Carolina, USA. March.

Carrillo, E. Unplanned tourism and its impact on wildlife in Costa Rica. International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Bi-

ology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Herzog, P. and C. Vaughan. The role of private nature reserves in the conservation of biological diversity in Costa Rica. International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Marineros, L. and C. Vaughan. Scarlet macaw nesting in Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica. International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

McCoy, M. Irrigated rice cultivation and water fowl: Methods to reduce the conflict. International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Mo, C. Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean: A network of training, research and outreach programs serving Latin America. Nature Conservation: The role of networks. Geraldton, Australia. May.

Naranjo, E. Preliminary study on tapir ecology in a tropical rain forest of Costa Rica. II Latin-American Therological Congress. La Habana, Cuba. June

Sáenz, J., H. Espach and C. Vaughan. Is a second reproductive period in coatimundis (*Nasua narica*) in the tropical dry forest a response to predation? International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Sáenz, J., C. Vaughan and H. Espach. The coatimundi (*Nasua narica*) as a seed disperser in the tropical dry forest in Santa Rosa National Park, Costa Rica. International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Torrealba, I., E. Naranjo, J. Villareal y H. Cháves. Strategies for peccary conservation in an isolated tropical rainforest. (Poster). International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Vaughan, C. Linking neotropical wildland biodiversity conservation and local human community stability in Costa Rica. Nature Conservation: The role of networks. Geraldton, Australia. May.

Vaughan, C. Diversity and conservation of the mastofauna in Central America. Part of symposium on "State of the conservation of mammals in Latin America". 75th Meeting of the Society of Mastrozoology. July.

Vaughan, C. Dry season waterhole utilization by wildlife species in tropical dry forests and management implications. International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Wong, G. and E. Carrillo. Strategies for conservation of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii citrinellus*) in Costa Rica. International Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology and the Association for Tropical Biology. Universidad de Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. June.

Wong, G. and E. Carrillo. Evaluation of tourist impact on squirrel monkeys in Manuel Antonio. 1st Meeting of Specialists in Sustainable Wildlife Use of the IUCN. Argentina. January.

C. Mo

III Latin American Conference of Wildlife Management Graduate Programs, Córdoba, Argentina. Standing left to right: Gustavo Reati (Arg.), unidentified, Frank Rivera (USFWS), M. Di Mare (CR), unidentified, Geraldo Wilson (Brazil), Ma. Drummond (Brazil), Donald Taphorn (Ven) and Gilberto Cintrón (USFWS).

1995

Canales, A. Restoring natural habitats for wildbirds on Lake Titicaca Bay, Puno, Peru. V Congress of Neotropical Ornithology. Asunción, Paraguay. August.

Canales, A. Populations of migratory birds on Lake Titicaca, Puno, Peru. V Congress of Neotropical Ornithology. Asunción, Paraguay. August.

Drews, C. Ethological considerations for wildlife rehabilitation and release program. Workshop on Rehabilitation and Release of Wildlife/International Congress of Universities for Sustainable Development. San José, Costa Rica. November.

Hernández, D. Monitoring resident and migratory birds on the Atlantic coast of Costa Rica. V Congress of Neotropical Ornithology. Asunción, Paraguay. August.

López, J. E. Food habits of frugivorous bats and their participation in seed dispersion. X International Conference on Research of Bats and XXV North American Symposium on Research of Bats. Boston, Massachusetts.

Mo, C. Diseases and other veterinary aspects associated with wildlife introductions. Workshop on Rehabilitation and Release of Wildlife/International Congress of Universities for Sustainable Development. San José, Costa Rica. November.

Vaughan, C. The scarlet macaw in the central Pacific, Costa Rica: Will international conservation dollars cause its extinction? VII Annual Meeting of the Society for Conservation Biology. Fort Collins, Colorado, USA. June.

Vaughan, C. Reintroduction as a conservation strategy for psittacids. Workshops on Rehabilitation and Release of Wildlife/International Congress of Universities for Sustainable Development. San José, Costa Rica. November.

1996

Fallas, J. Biodiversity and the Scientific Agenda of IAI. Advisory Workshop on the Participation of Central American Countries at the Interamerican Institute for Global Change. (Presenter). Hotel Irazú. San José. April.

Mo, C. Commercialization of sea turtle eggs: The case of Ostional,

Costa Rica. (Presenter). Symposium on the Sustainable Use of Wildlife. Cincinnati, Ohio, USA.

Torrealba, I. Talk on the advances of project 024314 and on the academic work of PRMVS to the DINIRA groups (Ecological University Group and ASOVEM (Venezuelan Association for the Study of Mammals). 46th Annual Convention of the Venezuelan Association for the Advancement of Science.

STAFF AND STUDENT PUBLICATIONS

1993

Aráuz, M., C. L. Mo and E. Vargas. 1993. Preliminary evaluation of Olive Ridley sea turtle egg commerce from Ostional Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. *Marine Turtle Newsletter* 63:17-20.

Carrillo, E. and C. Vaughan. 1993. Tourism influence on the behavior of the raccoon in Manuel Antonio National Park, Costa Rica. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 41:843-848.

Castro, J. C. and M. Aráuz. 1993. Olive Ridley Turtles observed with notches cut in marginal scutes in Ostional, Costa Rica. *Marine Turtle Newsletter* 61:24.

Drews, C. 1993. The concept and definition of dominance in animal behaviour. *Behaviour* 125:283-313.

Hernández, D. and J. Gómez-L. 1993. Aquatic flora of the Palo Verde marsh. Universidad Nacional Editorial, Heredia, Costa Rica. 132 pp.

Hernández, D. and J. Zook. 1993. Northward migration of peregrine falcons (*Falco peregrinus*) along the Caribbean coast of Costa Rica. *The Journal of Raptor Research* 24:123-125.

Johnson, W. and C. Vaughan. 1993. Habitat use of small terrestrial rodents in the Costa Rican highlands. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 41:521-527.

Martínez, D. R., J. R. Rau and F. M. Jáksic. 1993. Numerical response and diet selectivity in foxes (*Pseudalopex* spp) faced with a prey decrease in Northern Chile. *Revista Chilena de Historia Natural* 66:195-202.

Rangel-Salazar, J. L. y Enriquez-Rocha, P. L. 1993. Nest record and dietary items for the black hawk-eagle (*Spizaetus tyrannus*) from the Yucatán Peninsula. *The Journal of Raptor Research* 27:121-122.

Rau, J. 1993. Puma (*Felis concolor*) predation on the pudu (*Pudu pudu*) and European hare (*Lepus capensis*) in temperate rainforests in southern South America. Pages 602-604 in I. D. Thompson, ed. Proceedings XXI International Union of Game Biologists XXI Congress. Halifax, N.S., Canada.

Rau, J., D. R. Martínez and A. Muñoz-Pedrerros. 1993. Trophic ecology of pumas in southern South America. Pages 602-604 in J. Bissonette and P. Krausman, eds. Integrating People and Wildlife for a Sustainable Future. Proceedings of the First International Wildlife Management Congress. The Wildlife Society, Bethesda, Maryland, USA. 697 pp.

Sáenz, J. 1993. The tourist: Socio-economic impact for natural resources in Manuel Antonio National Park. *Ciencias Ambientales* 9:56-164.

Vaughan, C. 1993. The Global Forum: Power to the people in Rio de Janeiro ECO 92. *Ciencias Ambientales* 10:28-38.

Vaughan, C. 1993. Human population and wildlife: A Central American focus. *Trans. 58th North American Wildl. & Natur. Resour. Conf.* 55:129-136.

Vaughan, C. 1993. The state of biodiversity in Costa Rica. *In IX National Congress of Agronomy and Natural Resources. College of Agricultural Engineers.* San José, Costa Rica. 11 pp.

1994

- Allsteadt, J. C.** 1994. Nesting ecology of *Caiman crocodilus* in Caño Negro, Costa Rica. *Journal of Herpetology* 28:12-19.
- Allsteadt, J. C. and C. Vaughan.** 1994. Food habits of Central American caiman in Caño Negro Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. *Vida Silvestre Neotropical* 3:24-29.
- Allsteadt, J. C. y C. Vaughan.** 1994. Habitat selection by the Central American caiman in Caño Negro Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. *Brenesia* 38:76-72.
- Allsteadt, J. C. y C. Vaughan.** 1994. Population estimates of Central American caiman in Caño Negro Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. *Brenesia* 38:72-77.
- Aráuz, M.** 1994. *Eretmochelys imbricata* (Hawksbill): Reproduction. *Herpetological Review* 25:24.
- Aráuz, M. and R. A. Morera.** 1994. Examination of dead juvenile *Eretmochelys imbricata* (Hawksbill). *Marine Turtle Newsletter* 64:26.
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GRAY LITERATURE AND TECHNICAL REPORTS

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SHORT-COURSES, WORKSHOPS AND CONGRESSES ORGANIZED BY PRMVS

1993

- January. Workshop. B. Middleton from Southern Illinois University - Carbondale with **M. McCoy** organized a course showing the V Promotion students a histological technique to identify and analyze food items in waterfowl scats.
- March. Workshop. **G. Wong** y **E. Carrillo** organized the workshop "Importance of research in the planning of conservation areas". The National Parks Service of Costa Rica and INBio were co-organizers. Costa Rica.
- March. Workshop. **J. Fallas** was Universidad Nacional coordinator of the II National Workshop on Interpretation of Radar Data. Financed by the National Geographic Institute and the Canadian Space Agency. Costa Rica.
- May. Congress. **M. Carbonell**, with aid from The International Council for Bird Preservation (ICBP) and the Costa Rican National Museum, organized the First National Ornithological Congress. This included the founding of the Costa Rica Ornithological Association (AOCR). Over 22 presentations and 12 posters were presented. Heredia, Costa Rica. (See Presentations at Professional Meetings). Attendance 150.
- July. Seminar. **G. Wong** was a member of the organizing committee of the "Environmental Seminar and Superior Education in Central America", organized by the Universidad Nacional and the Consortium of North and Central American universities. Heredia, Costa Rica.
- September. International Congress. **PRMVS** was local host and **C. Vaughan** was local coordinator and part of the steering committee of the First International Congress for Wildlife Manage-

ment (theme "Integrating People and Wildlife for a Sustainable Future"), organized by The Wildlife Society. He chaired the "Session 5: Education and Effective Technology Transfer".

PRMVS, the IUCN and Costa Rica Wildlife and Parks Services were in-country hosts. Fifteen sessions with over 180 papers and 300 posters were given (see Publications section for PRMVS participation). Attendance 900 from 75 countries.

September. Workshop. **M. I. Di Mare** and **J. Sáenz** were coorganizers of the workshop, "Wildlife management on farms", carried out in conjunction with the First International Congress for Wildlife Management. Guest speakers included: Dr. J. G. Teer and Dr. N. J. Silvy of the Wildlife Society. Attendance 45.

October 11-17. Workshop. **M. McCoy** organized an international workshop that took 7 small-scale rice farmers from Guanacaste province to the Sacramento Valley, California. The farmers were given talks by the director of the Biggs Experimental Station, local farmers and extensionists from UC-Davis on current technology for irrigated rice cultivation in California.

November. Workshop. **J. Rau** organized the workshop "Ecology and conservation of birds of prey" at the III International Congress on Natural Resource Management: Integrated approach for development (also titled V Symposium on Wildlife Management). This congress was organized by the Wildlife Society of Chile. Pucón, Temuco, Chile.

1994

June. **C. Vaughan**, Lizbeth Espinoza from the Center for Judicial Rights, and T. Ankersen from University of Florida Law School organized the workshop on Wildland and Wildlife Legislation carried out in PRMVS. Over 15 guest lecturers were present, including: Dr. Richard Hamann, professor of law at the University of Florida; Carlos Manuel Rodríguez, lawyer for INBIO and other members of the Costa Rican Bar. Attendance 20 persons from 10 countries.

October. **C. Vaughan** organized a workshop-seminar in the central Pacific region of Costa Rica which aimed at producing a regional strategy for the protection and conservation of the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) population found there. Local residents, tour operators, government officials, local municipality and university professionals participated. PRMVS participants included: **E. Vargas**, **G. Wong**, **J. Fallas**, **D. Hernández** and **C. Vaughan**. Attendance 25.

1995

February 23-26. Workshop. **E. Carrillo** and **G. Wong** organized the workshop "Research Methods and Techniques for Wildlife in Guatemala", to undergraduate students from both the Universidad del Valle and Universidad de San Carlos. They were invited by the FIIT (Interamerican Foundation for Tropical Research). Humedal del Manchón-Guamuchal, Guatemala.

March 6-7. **The Teledetection and Geographical Information Systems Laboratory (TELESIG)** organized the First Seminar-Workshop on Information, Teledetection and Global Positioning Systems in Costa Rica. This activity was carried out as part of the project of "Gap Analysis of Diversity of Biological Resources", financed by USAID.

May. **C. Mo**, **C. Vaughan**, **D. Hernández** and **E. Vargas** of PRMVS gave a training course in Fundamentals of Conservation Biology to personal of the La Amistad-Pacific Conservation Area at the Scientific Research Station Henri Pittier. The short-course was organized by PRMVS and INBio. Attendance 25.

June 4-7. Workshop. **G. Wong** coordinated the workshop "Perspectives of conservation of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii citrinellus*) in Costa Rica". Y. Matamoros of the National Zoological Park, D. Castelfranco of the Fundación Manuel Antonio and J. A. Salazar (director of Manuel Antonio National Park) with the collaboration of the Captive Breeding Specialist Group of the IUCN and the Regional Office of the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock. Quepos, Puntarenas.

July. Workshop. **W. Segura** coordinated the workshop, "First Workshop-Seminar on the Sustainable Development of the Area between Palo Verde and Rincon de la Vieja National Parks. Organized by the Environment Technical Group and financed by the National Bank and the Gran Chorotega Foundation.

July. Workshop. **M. McCoy** co-organized a 2-day agricultural exchange session with G. Frankie, University of California, Berkeley. J. E. Hill agricultural extensionist from University of California, Davis, gave talks and field visits to a dozen small-scale and large-scale rice farmers in Cañas and Bagaces, Guanacaste.

August 5-11. Neotropical Ornithological Congress. Asunción, Paraguay. **N. López**, PRMVS graduate, was executive secretary of the V Neotropical Ornithological Congress.

August 13-16. Short-Course. **M. Aranda**, Mexican biologist and graduate of PRMVS, gave a short-course on identification of mammal tracks in Corcovado National Park. Students included Costa Rican park guards and graduate students of the VII promotion of PRMVS.

October 16-18. **C. Vaughan** and guest lecturer Stan Tomkiewicz, Jr. of Telonics Telemetry-Electronics Consultants, organized the International Workshop on Radio Telemetry Systems at PRMVS. Attendance 20 participants from 11 countries.

November. Workshop. **C. Drews** organized the "Workshop on Rehabilitation and Release of Wildlife" as part of the International Congress of Universities on Sustainable Development. **C. Drews**, **C. Mo** and **C. Vaughan** participated as speakers and students from the VII Promotion attended. Attendance 30.

Short course. **D. Hernández** organized the short-course "Techniques for Terrestrial Bird Monitoring", given to personal of the Cordillera Volcánica Central Conservation Area and La Amistad Conservation Area in the installations of the CCC (Caribbean Conservation Corporation) in Tortuguero, Costa Rica. It was funded by Partners in Flight and the Costa Rican National Parks Service assisted in field arrangements. Coorganizers included: US Forest Service and the Point Reyes Observatory. Instructors were: **D. Hernández**, **J. Zook**, **C. J. Ralph**, **D. Evans** and **B. Miia**.

TELESIG offered a training course in Geographical Information Systems to five employees of the Volcánica Central Conservation Area during a four-week period.

1996

C. Mo was instructor and Coordinator of the IV Course in Biology and Management of Sea Turtles, in Playa Nancite, in the Guanacaste Conservation Area, for 15 students of MINAE, national and international NGOs, scholars from the University of Panama and the Central American University of Nicaragua, and staff from national parks in Nicaragua.

J. Fallas organized the one-day Conference of ARC-INFO and ERDAS Users in Costa Rica, held at the Hotel Europa Zurquí in San José. Moderator and speaker. He also gave a talk about codes and standards of digital databases in Costa Rica.

J. Fallas gave a five-day course on Geographic Information Systems and decision-making to staff of the Central Volcanic Range Conservation Area.

J. Fallas gave a postgraduate course on Geographic Information Systems with an emphasis on IDRISI, Roots and ARC-INFO PC at the Central American University in Nicaragua.

August. **I. Torrealba** and **C. Vaughan** coordinated the workshop, "Environment, Culture and Fun with Conservation, Carara 1996.", in the town of Quebrada Ganada. The three-day workshop was part of the course, "Environmental Education and Communication Technology." With the VII promotion.

September 3-6. **J. Sáenz** coordinated the workshop, "Deciphering Mammal Footprints," for park guards of the Guanacaste and Tempisque Conservation Areas. The workshop had the support of the Costa Rica Civil Service.

DOCUMENTARY FILMS

"Case of the missing coats". 1993. Documentary on natural history of Pizotes. BBC and National Geographic productions with assistance of **J. Sáenz** as the scientific advisor.

"The Automatic Bird-scared". 1994. Documentary on research, management, and extension dealing with the problem of duck depredation of rice seed in Guanacaste. Produced by the Audiovisual and Teaching Aid Unit of the Universidad Nacional, directed by **Álvaro Camacho** with assistance of **M. McCoy**, principle researcher of this university project. (16 min.)

"So That We Aren't Forgotten" is a series of television 60-second spots created and produced by **Sonia Mayela Rodríguez** of the Audiovisual Office of UNED, **G. Wong** and **J. Sáenz** of PRMVS, starting in 1994. The objective of the series was to produce one-minute spots on the following endangered species: white-lipped peccary, squirrel monkey, spider monkey, Bairds tapir, great curassow, iguana, jaguar, puma, margay, crocodile, chachalaca, roseate spoonbill, jabiru, and the collared peccary. These miniprograms are now being shown on regular commercial television.

"Crossroads at Nancite". 1995. Documentary on wildlife use of the

A troop of pizotes during filming of the documentary, "Case of the missing coats", Santa Rosa National Park.

Nancite Basin and beach during the dry season. Produced by the British Broadcasting Corporation with assistance of **J. Sáenz** as the scientific advisor. (35 min.)

EXTENSION

1993

March. **C. Mo** and **M. Aráuz** and 18 other marine turtle specialists participated in the 7-day expedition organized by Dr. David Owens and Texas A&M University (TAMU) to study the Ridley sea turtle. Pacific Ocean.

April. Workshop. **J. Fallas** was invited visiting professor by the Nature Conservancy for Nature Conservation Week in the Dominican Republic, and gave the following course: "Changes in the size and condition of vegetation", and "Use of remote sensing and aerial photographs". Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic.

July. **I. Torrealba** participated in the second census of howler monkeys and collared peccaries in La Selva Biological Station in Costa Rica. Over 80 high school students from the region were involved.

August. **J. Rau** and **T. Zúñiga** participated as corridor specialists in the Organization for Tropical Studies course: "Tropical Managed Ecosystems". San Vito, Costa Rica.

September. **I. Torrealba** presented three lectures on ecology of collared peccaries to national and foreign high school students based on her work at the La Selva Biological Station in Costa Rica. Attendance: 50 students.

November 22-24. **C. Mo** and **J. Fallas** participated as representatives of the PRMVS at the II Conference of Latin American Wildlife Management Programs, convened at Belo Horizonte, Brazil.

1994

G. Wong participated with representatives of the World Union for Nature (IUCN), Correspondence University (UNED), and the Conservation Areas System (SINAC) in the program, Community Participation in Wildlife Management in Costa Rica".

April 28-May 1. **C. Vaughan** was Costa Rican Natural Resource Representative for the Organization of American States at the multinational coordinating meeting with representatives from 20 countries in Washington, D.C.

1995

J. Fallas was technical advisor in tele-detection and geographical information systems to the Department of Natural Resources and Biological Conservation of the Panamerican Agricultural School, Honduras.

J. Fallas participated in a workshop of Geographical Information Systems organized by the Department of Planning of the General Direction of Planning and International Cooperation of the Ministry of Natural Resources, Energy and Mines of Costa Rica.

January 14. **M. I. Di Mare, Lise Caron** and **W. Segura** participated in the First Concentration of Farmers, Hunters and Authorities to Establish Methods and Applications of Wildlife Management. Organized by The Wildlife Foundation and the Chamber of Tourism of Cañas, Costa Rica.

April 5. **J. Fallas** gave the lecture, "Geographical information for OT" in the workshop "Diagnostic of the Actual State of the National Territory", organized by the Commission of Territorial Organization of the National System of Sustainable Development. Guápiles, Costa Rica.

July. **N. E. García Prezioso** (VI Promotion) gave two lectures about cacomisties, her thesis topic, to school children and their teachers in the Enrique Strachan School, Roble Alto, San José de la Montaña, Heredia, Costa Rica. Attendance 40.

1996

PRMVS staff participated reviewing the draft of the proposed Rican Law of Biodiversity and provided recommendations.

C. Mo Guest professor for a 10-hour course in Reptile Ecology and a 30-hour course in Environmental Program Management for the first course specializing in Conservation Management and Wildlife Production, at the Agrarian Sciences Faculty of Pará, Brazil.

February. **M. McCoy** participated in "Science Fridays," sponsored by the UNA public information office, with 30 journalists from the country and the UNA Rector, about research projects in rice plantations and the wetlands of Palo Verde National Park.

February. **M. McCoy** participated in an hour-long interview program on National Radio about the importance of grazing in Palo Verde National Park to control fires, stimulate reforestation and provide waterfowl habitat. Rice culture methods to reduce negative impacts on the environment were also discussed.

February. **M. McCoy** for the OTS Tropical Ecology course (undergraduate) in Palo Verde, coordinated a field exercise (the response of wetland vegetation with and without cattle) for 10 students and gave a presentation about wetland restoration.

February. **E. Vargas** and **I. Torrealba**. Coordinated the workshop "Environment education for kindergarten" for the Herradura, Mothers' Association. Seven students of PRMVS VII promotion participated and 10 teacher-mothers attended. Herradura, Pérez Zeledón.

March. **J. Sáenz** presented a talk to staff of the Osa Conservation Area about advances and early results of the project, "Relations Between Jaguars and Peccaries in Corcovado National Park."

April. **C. Vaughan** gave a presentation on the television program, "San Buenaventura" about the PRMVS macaw study in Carara.

April. **C. Vaughan** was a visiting professor for Latin America week at St. Olaf College, Northfield, Minnesota, USA.

May. **C. Vaughan** Coordinator of "Science Fridays" at UNA. Scarlet macaw in the Carara-Punta Leona area.

May. **C. Vaughan, C. Mo, D. Hernández,** and **E. Vargas** were guest professors for the course, "Fundamentals of Conservation Biology in the Osa Conservation Area.

June. **J. Sáenz** was advisor for field work done by student Rónald Mora, specializing in forest management. The work was done in Corcovado and lasted 30 days. The topic was to estimate jaguar density in the park. Central American Cattle Ranching School, Atenas.

July. **M. McCoy** at a Conservation Biology course of the University of California at Berkeley (undergraduate), gave talks in Bagaces, Guanacaste on controlling damage caused by ducks to rice crops and on wetland restoration.

September. **M. McCoy** participated in a one-hour documentary for the series "Sin Fronteras" produced by a national television company about waterfowl. The program aired nationally (Channel 7) in November.

November. **C. Vaughan** was the guest speaker at an event celebrating the Second Anniversary of the Alexander Skutcl at UNA's regional headquarters in Pérez Zeledón.

Group of school children at a PRMVS workshop.

BIODOC

Centro de Información en Vida Silvestre (Wildlife Documentation Center)

Director:	Enrique Quesada
Librarians:	Nuria Duran and Liliana Araya
E-mail:	biodoc@una.ac.cr
Web:	http://www.una.ac.cr/biodoc
Tel/Fax:	506/ 277 3472
Working schedule:	Mon-Fri, 8:00 am until 6:00 pm
Major Funding Source:	US Fish and Wildlife Service

In October of 1987, the Wildlife Documentation Center (BIODOC) was established with assistance from the U. S. Fish and Wildlife Service. It was officially inaugurated on February 1, 1988 by **Prince Philip, Duke of Edinburgh** and President of the World Wildlife Fund for Nature, and Dr. Carlos Araya Pochet, President of the Universidad Nacional.

BIODOC is oriented to assist the regional bibliographical needs of researchers, professors and students by providing books, scientific journals, reprints, bulletins, theses and unpublished "gray" literature concerning wildlife from all over the world, with emphasis in the Neotropics. It is also a reference center for professionals that are involved in decision-making processes in natural resources institutions.

Wildlife research in Latin America faces two major problems from an information point of view: (a) limited access to the existing scientific literature because of elevated book and journal subscription rates and a lack of libraries and specialized centers, and (b) limited access to literature from developing countries because many of these country's researchers don't publish their results, which instead are presented as "gray literature" or reports to universities, and governmental or non-governmental agencies with limited distribution.

Therefore, many Latin American scientists repeat research projects or are not aware of the "state-of-the-art" investigation because of a lack of access to the conventional and non-conventional literature.

The mission of BIODOC is to consolidate information into a documentation center that would be a leader in the organization and distribution of specialized wildlife information through bulletins, catalogs and direct loans, giving quality and efficient service to the user.

Objectives

The general objective of BIODOC is to recover and systematize the existing wildlife literature in Latin America; making it available to users.

Specific objectives include:

- To maintain organized and up-to-date bibliographical material
- To facilitate an excellent library collection
- To establish a reference and consultation service for Latin American professionals outside of Costa Rica
- To establish an information network to obtain "gray" literature in Latin America

- To inform the public about recent acquisitions through three types of bulletins: a) recent book purchases (monthly), b) periodic publications (yearly), and c) "gray literature" (yearly).
- To obtain, archive, and disseminate the non-conventional literature produced by Latin American wildlife researchers.
- To establish a reference service for national and foreign users, either through fax, e-mail, or INTERNET.
- To establish an information network to obtain non-conventional literature, especially from Central America.
- To provide assistance for finding subject, author, or title references.

To attain its objectives and give good service, BIODOC maintains a good collection of books, journals, periodical publications, non-conventional literature and special video collections.

To achieve the goals of the interlibrary loan, BIODOC maintains a constant relationship with libraries from local institutions, such as the Agricultural Center for Tropical Research and Teaching (CATIE: Centro Agronómico Tropical de Investigación y Enseñanza); the Interamerican Institute for Agricultural Cooperation (IICA: Instituto Interamericano de Cooperación para la Agricultura); the Universidad de Costa Rica system of libraries, documents and information; the main Universidad Nacional library, "Joaquín García Monge"; and the National Web of Agricultural and Livestock Information.

Communication is also maintained with regional institutions: the library from the Universidad Nacional Agraria de Nicaragua, the biological documentation center from the Universidad Equiel Zamora, in the occidental plains of Venezuela; the Forestry Sciences Library from the Universidad de los Andes, Mérida, Venezuela; and the Dry Forest Library, Guanacaste Costa Rica.

BIODOC offers the following services:

- **loan**-- Reading room loan of books, journals, "gray literature", periodical publications, and reprints which cover the wildlife field;
- **books**-- Over 3000 book titles on ecology, biology and management of birds, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, and plants;
- **scientific journals**-- Complete collections of several scientific journals (the Journal of Wildlife Management, Ecology, Journal of Mammalogy, Auk, Ecological Monographs, The Wilson Bulletin), partial collection of 270 others and subscriptions to 79 scientific journals;
- **reprints**-- Over 7000 reprints of wildlife related articles on file;
- **abstracts**-- Two important collections make BIODOC one of the most up-to-date wildlife documentation centers. The complete collection of Wildlife Review (1935-1995) and Zoological Records from 1974-1997 for reptiles, birds, mammals and amphibians;
- **"gray literature"**-- Over 1200 Latin American research projects are found in BIODOC, including technical reports, institutional reports, and theses (licenciature, master, and doctorate);
- **computerized data bases**-- The complete set of citations found in Wildlife Review plus our 7000 reprints and 700 "gray literature" documents are offered on one compact disk accessible with a "user-friendly" database microcomputer program which can retrieve citations by scientific name, author name, geographical region, or keywords.

Databases: a) "gray literature database", includes local data: graduation documents (licenciature and M.Sc. thesis from the Sciences of the Earth and Sea Faculty), and it includes 1724 records; b) the "reprints database" contains 6890 records; and c) Wildlife Review.

- **bulletin archive**-- BIODOC receives many reports from NGOs and other conservation groups;
- **documental archive**-- To complement the bibliographical information, BIODOC offers an archive of over 4000 Costa Rican newspaper clippings related to this theme;
- **interlibrary loan**-- This service is offered between other libraries in Costa Rica;
- **foreign requests**-- Up to 10 reprints per request and computerized searches of wildlife themes are mailed to solicitors. BIODOC is considering the possibility of sending larger documents if prepaid.

TELESIG

Laboratorio de Teledetección y Sistemas de Información Geográfica (Teledetection and Geographical Information Systems Laboratory)

TECHNOLOGY, SERVICE AND INFORMATION

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TELESIG is a specialized unit of the PRMVS and the Environmental Sciences School (EDECA: Escuela de Ciencias Ambientales). It has developed research projects, teaching and extension in Integrated Systems of Geographical Information since 1988.

The mission of **TELESIG** is to promote an ethical and sustainable use of information generated from either teledetection, GIS and from the global positioning in the Costa Rican and Central American society. This will be accomplished through training, research, technological transfer and by providing access to updated and accurate information.

Objectives

- To promote education and training in Teledetection, GIS and global positioning of professionals and students from MesoAmerica and the Caribbean.
- To promote the use of integrated GISs in the environmental management at a local, regional, national, and global level.
- To provide specialized services of Integrated GISs to the public and private sectors of Costa Rican society, as well as to the Central American and Caribbean regions.
- To contribute to the adoption of a professional ethic that promotes the access and interchange of digital information.
- To promote free access to information through electronic publication and INTERNET use.

The services the laboratory offers are:

- Creation of digital databases
- Digitalization
- Processing of satellite digital imagery (TM, Spot, ERS, RADARSAT)
- Education, use and training in service in GIS & GPS
- Electronical publication
- Vectorization from raster files (binaries or color)
- AM/FM Systems (automated mapping and service management)

TELESIG lab has participated in the following types of projects and activities:

- Management and monitoring of wildlife habitat
- Forest and soil management
- Environmental impact evaluations
- Cartography/digital mapping
- Watershed Management
- Biodiversity
- Wetlands inventory and monitoring
- Flora and fauna species distribution
- Wildlife and wildlands management
- Global change
- Environmental planning
- Hydric resources
- Land use planning
- Territorial planification of natural spaces
- Natural disasters

EQUIPMENT

The lab has two working areas of approximately 18m² and 36m², and a 4WD vehicle. Additionally, it has the following software and hardware equipment:

Computers:

- Pentium processors (70, 100 y 120 y 133 MHz; a 486 DX4 of 100 and a DX2 of 66 Mhz). Each computer holds hard disks of at least 1.3GB, 15" y 17" monitors, and 2MB memory video cards. Three 266Mhz Pentium II computers
- Portable computers: color 386SX and a monochromatic 386DX

Printers:

- Printers: HP PaintJet XL 300 Postscript, Epson LQ-570+ and laser HP 5L
- HP Design Jet 350C with 10MB RAM

Digitizers:

- Digitizer: MicroGrid III 36*42"
- Digitizers Rollup II GTCO of 20" * 24" and 24" * 36"

Drives, CD-Roms, CD-writers:

- Two ZipDrive 100 MB units and a Colorado Jumbo 250 ribbon unit
- Three CD-ROM units
- Two 1.0 GB IOMEGA Jazz units
- One EXABYTE 8200 ribbon unit
- One 4X CDs (CD-Writer)

GPS:

- One Trimbel/Pathfinder Global Positioning System with a base station

Software (licenses for 19 computer programs, some of which include):

- Corel-Draw V8.0 and Corel Word Perfect Suite V8.0
- Stat Most 3.0 W95 y NT for statistical analysis

- R2V (vectorizer)
- Map-X GIS/RS version 2.0
- Earth View de Atlantis Scientific System Group, Inc.
- ArcInfo V 7.1.1 and its extensions en a NT environment:
- Arc View GIS V 3.0a and its extensions:Gis Spatial Analyst, Gis Network Analyst
- MicroStation Versions 4.0, 5.0 and W95.
- Software from Intergraph Co. (SIG and image processors)

VIDA SILVESTRE NEOTROPICAL - VSN (Neotropical Wildlife)

Editors:	M. McCoy and C. Vaughan
Collaborators:	M. Carranza, Administrative Editor, and C. L. Mo, Editorial Assistant.
Financial support:	Universidad Nacional, World Wildlife Fund, U. S. Fish & Wildlife Ser- vice, Wildlife Conservation Soci- ety, and Organization of American States.
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Vida Silvestre Neotropical is a technical journal that was initiated to provide an alternative for Latin American scientists to publish relevant, high quality information in their own language. Manuscripts are accepted and published in the three most important languages in the region: Spanish, Portuguese or English. The journal aims to break down the language barrier that has often impaired Latin American scientists from publishing on an international level.

Vida Silvestre Neotropical is primarily dedicated to publishing high quality articles regarding wildlife research and management in the Neotropics and temperate South America. The journal aims to fill a void perceived by the international scientific community, especially in Latin America, for a journal that specialized in distributing recent information about conservation and management of natural resources.

The journal first appeared in 1987 as a biannual publication, funded by World Wildlife Fund, with support from W. Alton Jones Foundation, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and the IUCN. Two volumes with two numbers each were published (Vol 1 and 2). However, by 1990 it was discontinued for logistical reasons and time constraints. Efforts were then directed to reestablish it and production of the journal was offered to several Latin American wildlife institutions, the PRMVS being finally chosen.

During 1993 efforts were dedicated to reinstate the journal: Selection of the journal editors/coordinators, establishment of an office space, hiring of a full-time administrative editor, purchase of the necessary computer equipment, obtention of subscriptions, and consolidation of the revision process (assembling a body of associate editors, contact with authors of discontinued manuscripts, calls for new manuscripts, evaluation of new and formerly discontinued manuscripts). Most of the year was spent in getting manuscripts under revision and in obtaining subscriptions.

The 1st number of Vol. 3 was published in June 1994 and marketed at the Society for Conservation Biology Meeting in Guadalajara, Mexico. Since then, the process has successfully continued, with volumes 3 and 4 (with two numbers each) and volume 5 (6 numbers in all). Publications include 30 featured

articles, 12 short communications, and 35 book reviews.

Objectives and Policies

The overall objective of the Journal is to consolidate its circulation, via the Universidad Nacional, to the global scientific community.

The Journal publishes articles and notes about flora and fauna in their natural states in the terrestrial, freshwater, and marine environments of Latin America. In addition, the Journal includes research results about ecosystem, wildlands, and species management (including natural forests). *Vida Silvestre Neotropical* tries to meet the needs of professionals, technicians, students, and policy makers interested in conservation and management of neotropical wildlife.

The primary subject area of the journal is Neotropical wildlife management in the broadest sense. Geographically it includes Mexico, Central America, South America, and the Caribbean. The subject area includes wild flora and fauna, and terrestrial, freshwater and marine habitats (but it is not intended to cover marine fisheries).

Journal articles present new information and concepts resulting from wildlife and wildland research and management including such topics as: sustainable-use-management of wild flora and fauna, the conservation of endangered species and ecosystems, natural forest management, maintenance of biotic diversity, control of pest species, biological basis for the design of protected area systems, indigenous use of wildlife, research on wildlife biology or ecology, and biological inventories with broad or unique management implications. Descriptions of new techniques in wildlife research and management, such as new equipment, or new capture or survey methods are encouraged. The subject area includes matters related to wildland management, focusing primarily on the management of species or habitats.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT

The budget for PRMVS includes personnel, operation and student scholarship costs (Table 1). An average of US \$394,770/year was obtained during the 10 years of PRMVS existence. The two major funding agencies have been The National University (UNA) providing 50.3% of these funds, which cover principally personnel costs; and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) providing 20.2%. During the 1993-96 period, the UNA has increased its percent participation (from 50.3 to 59.9%), while there has been a decrease in the percent participation of USFWS (from 20.2 to 15.9%). In general, the amount of donations have decreased in the last 4 years. A few organizations have increased their donations (NFWF and MUTIS) (see averages in Table 1).

The other funding agencies have provided 29.5% of 1987-96 budget, and 24.2% of the 1993-96 period). There were some agencies with relatively small contributions that are not included in Table 1: the Costa Rican Wildlife Foundation, the British and the Colombian Governments, the Agency for International Development (US-AID), the Audubon Society, the Organization for Tropical Studies (OTS),

Project Lighthawk, the Wildlife Conservation Society and the National Science and Technology Council of Mexico (CONACYT).

Because of the decrease in donations, efforts are being directed towards obtaining funding for long-term planning of activities and priorities of PRMVS. This includes funding for scholarships, thesis work, hiring of personnel, competitive salaries for professors, training and extension activities (at the technical, pre-graduate and community levels), professional improvement for professors (exchanges, participation in international conferences, Ph.D. training, etc.). The diversification of funding sources has been key to the development of PRMVS and continues to be a necessity.

The program is also identifying sustainable ways of self-funding, which could include training workshops, short-courses, etc.

E. Tabilo

Table 1. Income to PRMVS in thousands of US dollars (1987-96):

Year	UNA	USFWS ^a	WWF	McArt	Noyes	DAAD ^b	OAS	FVS	NFWF	IRD	Mutis	Total
1987	118.5	75	30				20					243.5
1988	130.3	75	30			64	20					319.3
1989	125.5	183	61		36.6	48	20					474.1
1990	176.6	59.1	42.7		36.6	32	25					372.0
1991	243.3	100	43.7	75	36.8	48	25					571.8
1992	289.2	65	22.6	65			20					461.8
1993	269.4	55	10	55		21.6	20					431.0
1994	217.3	78.5	15			26.6	15					352.4
1995	267.6	50.3				22.6	16.9	9.4	55		54	475.8
1996	146.8	55.4	22.3			9.5				6.5	5.5	246.0
Total '87-'96	1984.5	796.3	277.3	195	110	272.3	181.9	9.4	55	6.5	59.5	3947.7
%	50.3	20.2	7.0	4.9	2.8	6.9	4.6	0.24	1.4	0.16	1.5	100.0
Average	198.5	79.6	27.7	19.5	11	27.2	18.2	0.91	5.5	0.6	5.9	394.8
Total '93-'96	901.1	239.2	47.3	55	0	80.3	51.9	9.4	55	6.5	59.5	1505.2
%	59.9	15.9	3.1	3.7	0	5.3	3.4	0.6	3.7	0.4	4.0	100
Average	225.3	59.8	11.8	13.7	0	20.1	113	2.4	13.8	1.6	14.9	376.3

DAAD=German Academic Exchange Program
FVS=Wildlife Foundation of Costa Rica

IRD= International Resources Development of England
UNA=National University
OAS=Organization of American States
WWF=World Wildlife Fund for Nature

McArt=MacArthur Foundation
Mutis=Spanish International Cooperation Agency
NFWF=National Fish & Wildlife Foundation
Noyes=Noyes Foundation
USFWS=U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service

^aUSFWS does not include donation to BIODOC.

^b(2) DAAD does not include scholarships directly paid by DAAD to students, nor registration fees paid to UNA.

PARTICIPATING INSTITUTIONS

Provided Funding Donations for PRMVS and Student Financial Support

Agency for International Development, Washington, D.C. (USAID)
Audubon Society
German Academic Exchange Program, Berlin, Germany (DAAD)
Idea Wild, Fort Collins, Colorado
International Resources Development of England
Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, North Carolina (OTS)
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C. (OAS)
Project Lighthawk, Santa Fe, New Mexico
Spanish International Cooperation Agency
United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Washington, D.C. (USFWS)
Wildlife Conservation Society, New York, New York (WCS)
World Wildlife Fund-US, Washington, D.C. (WWFUS)

Cooperative Agreements signed with PRMVS or UNA

Ministry of Environment and Energy (MINAE), Costa Rica
Experimental University of los Llanos, Guarane, Venezuela
Federal University of Santa Catarina, Brazil
Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, North Carolina
University of Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain
United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Washington, D.C.
University of Wisconsin-Madison, Wisconsin

Provided Fullbright, Sabbatical, or Visiting Professors

Organization for Migrations, United Nations, Geneva, Switzerland (OIM)
University of Florida, Gainesville, Florida
University of Los Lagos, Osorno, Chile
University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Massachusetts
University of Moncton, Edmunston, New Brunswick, Canada.
Washington State University, Pullman, Washington
Welder Wildlife Foundation, Sinton, Texas

Cooperative Projects (training, exchange, etc.)

Agency for International Development, Washington, D.C.
Clemson University, Clemson, South Carolina
Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, South Carolina
Ramsar Bureau, Gland, Switzerland
Southern Illinois University, Carbondale, Illinois
University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Massachusetts
U.S. Forest Service, Redwood Laboratory, Arcata, California
Welder Wildlife Foundation, Sinton, Texas

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PARTICIPATING INSTITUTIONS*

Provided Principle Funding Donations for PRMVS and Thesis Student Financial Support

Agency for International Development, Washington, D.C. (USAID).
Association of Field Ornithologists (AFO).
Fundación de Vida Silvestre, Costa Rica.
German Academic Exchange Service, Bonn, Germany (DAAD).
Idea Wild, Fort Collins, Colorado, USA.
Iberoamerican Cooperative Agency (ICA).
International Resources Development of England (IRD).
MANOMET, Center for Conservation Sciences (Birder's exchange Project).
Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, North Carolina, USA. (OTS).
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C., USA. (OAS).
Project Lighthawk, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA.
Rainforest Alliance.
Ramsar Bureau, Gland, Switzerland.
Spanish International Cooperation Agency (MUTIS).
Tieraerzliche Hochschule, Hannover, Germany.
United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Washington, D.C., USA. (USFWS).
United States National Fish and Wildlife Foundation, USA.
Wildlife Conservation Society, New York, New York, USA. (WCS).
World Wildlife Fund-US, Washington, D.C., USA. (WWF-US).
World Wildlife Fund-Regional Office, Costa Rica.

Cooperative Agreements signed with PRMVS or UNA.

Ministry of Environment and Energy (MINAE), Costa Rica.
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German Academic Exchange Service, Bonn, Germany (DAAD).
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United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Washington, D.C., USA.

Cooperative Projects (training, exchange, etc.).

Agency for International Development, Washington, D.C., USA. (US-AID).
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Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, South Carolina, USA.
Ramsar Bureau, Gland, Switzerland.
Rob & Bessie Welder Wildlife Foundation, Sinton, Texas, USA.
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University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Massachusetts, USA.
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